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Direct Hardware Circuit Transformation for Model Checking: Implementation and Impact Evaluation

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STUDENT DECLARATION

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Budapest, December 15, 2025

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student

Kivonat

Az elmúlt években a formális verifikáció területe mind az akadémiai kutatásban, mind az ipari gyakorlatban egyre nagyobb jelentőségre tett szert, mivel a szoftver- és hardverrendszerek helyessége és megbízhatósága kritikus fontosságú kérdéssé vált. A modellellenőrzés, amely e terület egyik központi technikája, automatizált módszert kínál a rendszer tulajdonságainak szigorú ellenőrzésére. Ennek elérése érdekében a modellellenőrzők a bemeneti modellt formális ábrázolásba (pl. Control Flow Automata, avagy CFA) alakítják át, majd kimerítően felfedezik az összes lehetséges viselkedést egy adott tulajdonság ellenőrzése érdekében.

A BTOR2 a legkorszerűbb, szószintű modellellenőrzési formátum, amely bitpontosan írja le a hardver áramköröket. Ahelyett, hogy a hardverdizájnokot közvetlenül komplex hardverleíró nyelveken, például Verilogban kellene ellenőrizni, a BTOR2 rögzített és egyértelmű szemantikát biztosít. Ez megkönnyíti a modellellenőrzők fejlesztőinek a munkáját, akik így magára a modellellenőrzésre koncentrálhatnak.

Számos hardveres modellellenőrző áll rendelkezésre, amelyek közvetlenül ellenőrzik a BTOR2 áramköröket (pl. ABC, AVR). Más alkalmazási területeken, például a szoftvereknél, azonban olyan új technikákat fejlesztettek ki, amelyek nem feltétlenül állnak rendelkezésre ezekben a hardveres ellenőrzőkben. Ezen hiány pótlásában segít a Btor2C eszköz, amely a BTOR2 áramköröket C programokká alakítja át, így lehetővé téve, hogy számos szoftveres ellenőrző is képes legyen a BTOR2 ellenőrzésére. E munka eredményei azt mutatták, hogy a szoftverellenőrzők ugyanazon időkorlát mellett olyan hibákat tudtak megtalálni, amelyeket a hardverellenőrzők nem.

A Btor2C használata azonban egy további átalakítási lépést jelent a C kódban, ami hatással lehet a hatékonyságra, miközben növeli az egyes lépésekkel kapcsolatos implementációs problémák esélyét. Az ismétlődő átalakítások és a végeredményre szabott optimalizálások hátráltathatják a modellellenőrzési elemzés teljesítményét. Ezenkívül a forráskód és a hardver áramkörök között alapvető különbségek vannak - például a BTOR2 tetszőleges szélességű bitvektorokkal dolgozik. Bár a Btor2C empirikusan validálásra került, a fent említett különbségek miatt az átalakítás nem triviális, ami implementációs problémákra hajlamossá teszi.

Jelenleg nincs olyan eszköz, amely képes lenne közvetlenül ellenőrizni mind a C programokat, mind a BTOR2 áramköröket, ami megakadályozza a hatékonyság megbízható összehasonlítását. Ezért ebben a dolgozatban a Theta modellellenőrzési keretrendszerben megvalósítom a BTOR2-ről CFA-ra történő közvetlen átalakítást. Így a bitvektor típusok közvetlenül használhatják a megoldás alapjául szolgáló SMT megoldók azonos szemantikájú típusait, valamint a ciklusok is természetesen kifejezhetőek gráfhuorkként. Továbbá a közvetlen transzformáció lehetővé tette számomra, hogy a CFA-n BTOR2-specifikus optimalizálási lépéseket implementáljak.

Arra alapozva, hogy a Theta már képes volt C programokat CFA-vá alakítani, megterveztem és megvalósítottam egy összehasonlító kiértékelést, amelyben ugyanazon algoritmusok teljesítményét elemeztem különböző transzformációs láncok használata esetén. A megbízható értékelés érdekében a Hardware Model Checking Competition legkorszerűbb

benchmark gyűjteményben elérhető hardver áramköröket használtam, amelyek átfogó és széles körben elfogadott alapot nyújtanak a hardverellenőrző eszközök teljesítmények összehasonlításához.

Abstract

In recent years, formal verification has gained increasing importance in both academic research and industrial practice, as the correctness and reliability of software and hardware systems have become critical concerns. Model checking, one of the central techniques in this domain, provides an automated way to rigorously verify system properties. To achieve this, model checkers transform the input model into a formal representation (e.g., Control Flow Automata) and then exhaustively explore all possible behaviors to verify a given property.

BTOR2 is the state-of-the-art, word-level model checking format, which describes hardware circuits in a bit-precise manner. Instead of verifying hardware designs directly on complex hardware description languages such as Verilog, BTOR2 provides fixed and unambiguous semantics, enabling tool developers to focus more on the model checking analysis.

Several available hardware model checkers can directly verify BTOR2 circuits (e.g., ABC, AVR). However, researchers of other application domains, such as software, have been developing new techniques not necessarily available in hardware verifiers. To bridge this gap, the tool Btor2C has been developed to transform BTOR2 circuits to C programs, making a wide array of software verifiers capable of verifying BTOR2. Results of that work have shown that software verifiers can find bugs that hardware verifiers were not able to find, given the same time limit.

However, utilizing Btor2C introduces an extra transformation step to C code, which might affect effectiveness, while also increasing the chance of implementation issues with each step. The repeating transformations and end-result specific optimizations might hinder the performance of the model checking analysis. Furthermore, software code and hardware have fundamental differences (e.g., arbitrary-width bit-vector types in BTOR2). Although Btor2C is empirically validated, the transformation is not trivial due to the above-mentioned differences, making it more prone to hidden issues.

Currently, no single tool is capable of directly model checking both C programs and BTOR2 circuits, prohibiting a fair comparison of effectiveness. Thus, in this work, I implement the direct transformation from BTOR2 to CFAs in the Theta model checking framework. With this direct transformation, bit-vector types can directly use the underlying SMT solver types with the same semantics, and cyclic behavior can be expressed naturally as graph loops. Furthermore, the direct transformation allowed me to implement BTOR2-specific optimization passes on the CFA.

With Theta's ability to transform C programs into CFAs, I designed and executed a comparative evaluation of algorithm performance under different transformation chains. For a reliable evaluation, I used the hardware circuits available in the state-of-the-art benchmark suite of the Hardware Model Checking Competition, which provides a comprehensive and widely accepted basis for comparing hardware verification tools.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Over the past decade, our understanding of and techniques for hardware verification have evolved significantly. Traditionally, hardware verification relied on simulation, where system behavior is tested against expected outcomes. [16] While effective for small designs, simulation cannot guarantee full coverage and often fails to expose corner cases in complex circuits.

To overcome these limitations, *formal verification* uses mathematical and logical techniques to prove or disprove the correctness of hardware designs. The main approaches are *theorem proving* [13, 23], *equivalence checking* [24], and *model checking* [1, 18]. I will focus on model checking, which is widely adopted for sequential hardware. Model checking automatically determines whether a design satisfies its formal specification or produces a counterexample. Typically, the design is represented by a formal model (e.g., a transition system), and invariant verification ensures that the given properties hold in all reachable states.

Recent research has shown that translating hardware models into software and verifying them with software model checkers can reveal bugs not found by even state-of-the-art hardware analyzers such as ABC or AVR [14, 22, 27]. The creators of the original idea performed a transformation from *Verilog* to *C*. [27] Their experimental results showed that by using software analyzers the model checking process could be more than an order of magnitude faster.

Ever since then, several approaches have aimed to translate hardware description languages into higher-level software representations, allowing existing software verifiers, such as CPACHECKER [4] and ESBMC [21], to perform model checking indirectly. One notable effort is BTOR2C [8], which converts BTOR2 circuits into C programs, enabling a wide range of software verification tools to analyze them. BTOR2 has become the de facto standard intermediate representation for hardware model checking, officially adopted as the input format of the Hardware Model Checking Competition (HWMCC) [12]. It provides fixed, unambiguous semantics and aligns closely with SMT-LIB [3], also making it a robust intermediate format for bit-level languages such as AIGER and Verilog.

Motivation While BTOR2C enables indirect verification, it introduces an additional translation step into C, which can reduce efficiency and increase the risk of transformation errors. Each intermediate step adds complexity and may hinder analysis performance due to redundant optimizations or semantic mismatches. Moreover, hardware and software differ fundamentally. For instance, BTOR2 supports arbitrary-width bit-vector types

that have no direct C equivalent. Although empirically validated, BTOR2C’s translation remains nontrivial and potentially error-prone.

To address these issues, this work implements a direct transformation from BTOR2 to control-flow automata (CFA) [5] within the THETA [33] model checking framework. This approach preserves the exact semantics of bit-vectors through the SMT solver, naturally represents cyclic hardware behavior as graph loops, and enables BTOR2-specific optimizations directly on the CFA, thus eliminating the need for intermediate C code and improving overall analysis efficiency.

The objective of this thesis is to conduct a comparative analysis and assess whether a dedicated BTOR2 frontend offers superior efficiency compared to translation-based verification workflows.

Contributions The outline of this work is as follows:

- In Chapter 2, I provide an overview of the necessary background concepts, including formal verification techniques, the BTOR2 format, control-flow automata, and the THETA framework.
- In Chapter 3, I present the implementation of the BTOR2-to-CFA transformation within the THETA framework, providing a unified verification environment capable of analyzing both hardware and software systems.
- Chapter 4 presents a comprehensive evaluation of the direct BTOR2 frontend, empirically validating its efficiency advantages. This chapter provides a detailed comparative analysis of the formal representations generated by direct versus indirect transformations, alongside a performance benchmark of the various verification algorithms supported by THETA [33]. Furthermore, it examines the specific impact of BTOR2-oriented optimizations on overall verification efficiency.

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter provides an overview of the fundamental concepts and tools relevant to my thesis. First, Section 2.1 introduces model checking, the central verification technique underlying this work. Next, Section 2.2 presents control-flow automata, the modeling formalism employed throughout the project. Section 2.3 describes the essential components of the BTOR2 language used in the implementation; for a complete description of the BTOR2 syntax, please refer to the original publication [29]. Subsequently, Section 2.4 discusses the motivation for applying software verification algorithms to hardware flows, highlighting the distinction between direct and indirect transformation approaches. Finally, Section 2.5 introduces the THETA framework, which serves as the foundation for the implementation presented in this thesis.

2.1 Model Checking

The challenge of verifying programs without executing or deploying them has been a central research topic since the late 20th century [25]. One of the principal approaches addressing this problem is *formal verification*, which aims to provide mathematically rigorous proofs for the correct operation of computer programs [20].

Among formal verification techniques, *model checking* [1, 18] has become one of the most widely used and practically applicable methods. Given a software or hardware system, model checking systematically and exhaustively explores all possible executions for every possible input to determine whether specified properties hold. Unlike testing or simulation, which inspects only a limited subset of behaviors, model checking offers **exhaustive verification** – meaning if a property is satisfied, it holds for all possible executions of the model; if it is violated, the model checker produces a **counterexample** that reflects an actual execution leading to an error state.

Model checking provides an automated framework for verifying systems, including concurrent and finite-state models, by performing an efficient symbolic or explicit traversal of the system’s **state space**. Each state represents a unique configuration of the system’s variables, while transitions correspond to execution steps. The model checker systematically determines whether safety and liveness constraints hold within this state graph [16].

Typical properties include detecting *assertion violations*, *out-of-bounds indexing*, and *arithmetic overflows*. In this work, the focus is primarily on the **reachability property**, which concerns determining whether a given “bad” or error state is reachable from

the initial configuration of the system. Demonstrating that no such state can be reached constitutes a proof of safety for the given model.

While model checking is powerful, it suffers from the well-known **state-space explosion problem** [19]. The number of possible states grows exponentially with the number of variables in the system. For example, a program with three 32-bit input variables already has

$$2^{32} \cdot 2^{32} \cdot 2^{32} = 2^{96}$$

possible input combinations, making exhaustive exploration computationally infeasible for large-scale systems. This challenge has motivated extensive research into more scalable techniques, such as symbolic model checking [15], abstraction and refinement methods [10], and SAT-based [3] approaches.

2.2 Control-Flow Automata

Many programming languages tend to have ambiguities and complex structures that may help the developers express themselves more concisely, but are hard to handle in low-level algorithms. For this purpose, input programs must be transformed into an unambiguous formal representation that accurately captures their behaviour. Common forms of these formal models include transition systems, which describe states and their possible transitions, and automata, which represent system behavior through states and input-driven transitions.

To perform this transformation, software model checking toolchains typically employ specialized frontends that translate the source code into these formal models, so the so called “backend” can analyze it and apply mathematical and algorithmic reasoning to system properties in a precise and efficient way.

A widely used formalism is the **Control-Flow Automata (CFA)** [5], which is formally defined as:

Definition (Control-flow automata). A control-flow automaton is a tuple

$$CFA = (V, L, l_0, E)$$

where

- $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ is a set of variables with domains $D_{v_1}, D_{v_2}, \dots, D_{v_n}$,
- L is a set of program *locations*, usually modeling the program counter,
- $l_0 \in L$ is the *initial* program location (entry point),
- $E \subseteq L \times Ops \times L$ is a set of directed *edges* representing the *operations* that are executed when control flows from the source location to the target. *Ops* can either be *assignments* or *assumptions*. Assignments change a single variable – there is a special case called *havoc*, which is a nondeterministic assignment – and assumptions check a condition.

Figure 2.1 illustrates a simple control-flow automaton (CFA). The blue location l_0 denotes the *initial state* of the program. It is important to distinguish between *states* and *locations* in the context of CFAs. In this example, there are two variables, a and b , each assigned a value. Together, these values define a *concrete data state*. If the variables instead

Figure 2.1: Simple representation of a Control-Flow Automata (CFA).

represented sets of possible values determined by the program’s constraints, they would form *abstract states*.

The red location represents the *error location*, which corresponds to a unsafe program states. A *counterexample* demonstrates a feasible path from an initial state to such an unsafe state, whereas a proof of safety ensures that no unsafe state is ever reachable. Although reachability queries can, in principle, treat any state as unsafe, it is common to restrict these to specific *unsafe locations*, since program specifications are often expressed as assertions in the code.

An execution of the program corresponds to a *concrete trace*: a sequence of concrete states and transitions within the CFA’s state space. These traces can be projected onto the graph defined by the CFA’s locations and edges to form directed paths, which correspond to specific executions of the program. A trace that leads to an error location represents a counterexample, demonstrating how the property violation can occur.

2.3 The Hardware Model Checking Format BTOR2

Hardware model checking is a verification technique used to ensure that digital hardware designs behave correctly according to their specifications. It has been a long-established and highly successful application domain within formal methods, with early breakthroughs, such as bounded model checking (BMC) [10], demonstrating the practicality of applying SAT- and SMT-based reasoning to hardware verification problems.

In this domain, the goal is to check whether a hardware model – typically represented as a sequential circuit – satisfies certain logical properties. A sequential circuit is a digital

system composed of combinational logic (which determines outputs based solely on current inputs) and memory elements such as flip-flops or registers (which store the system’s state across clock cycles). Verification then involves exploring the circuit’s possible state transitions over time to ensure that unsafe or undesired (bad) states are never reachable. In the context of model-checking that is called *reachability safety*.

The Hardware Model Checking Competition (HWMCC) [12] serves as a benchmark for evaluating formal verification tools for hardware systems. A key innovation supporting this effort is BTOR2 [29], a word-level model checking format designed for bit-precise modeling of word-level sequential circuits. The BTOR2 language extends the previous bit-level AIGER [11] format with higher-level abstractions, making it ideal for various verification techniques. It introduces a simple, sorted, line-based syntax that is easy to parse and aligns with SMT-LIB [3] semantics for bit-vectors and arrays.

2.3.1 Syntax of BTOR2

The BTOR2 language identifies 2 entities called *sort* and *node*. Each line of code starts with a number, respectively *sid* (sort id) and *nid* (node id) which can be referenced in the subsequent lines.

A *sort* can be one of two types: a bit-vector of arbitrary width w , denoted by \mathcal{B}^w , or an array type. An array type is expressed as $\mathcal{A}^{I \rightarrow E}$, where I and E are bit-vector types representing the index and element sorts, respectively.

A *node* may correspond to an *input*, a *state*, or the *result* of applying an operator to other nodes. Inputs represent external signals provided to the BTOR2 circuit, while states correspond to the circuit’s memory elements. Typically, inputs have bit-vector types, whereas states may be either bit-vector or array types. In this report, I will focus only on the bit-vector cases.

Operators serve as the fundamental building blocks of a BTOR2 circuit. Each operator takes arguments of specific types and produces a result of a well-defined type. The general syntax for defining a BTOR2 operator is:

$$\langle \text{nid} \rangle \langle \text{op} \rangle \langle \text{sid} \rangle \langle \text{nid}_1 \rangle [\langle \text{nid}_2 \rangle [\langle \text{nid}_3 \rangle]]$$

This notation specifies that the node identified by *nid* stores the result of applying the operator *op* to one, two, or three operands. The resulting node has type *sid* and can be referenced by its identifier.

BTOR2 also includes constructs such as *init*, *next*, and *bad* for describing safety and reachability properties of sequential circuits. The *init* keyword defines initial states, while *bad* identifies unsafe or error states. The *next* construct specifies state transitions between consecutive time steps.

2.3.1.1 Count2 Example

In Listing 2.1 is a BTOR2 circuit that defines a simple finite state machine – a 3-bit counter – that starts from zero and increments by one at each time step.¹ Each line defines a node in the circuit, such as a constant, state, operation, or property.

```
1 1 sort bitvec 3
2 2 zero 1
3 3 state 1
4 4 init 1 3 2
5 5 one 1
6 6 add 1 3 5
7 7 next 1 3 6
8 8 ones 1
9 9 sort bitvec 1
10 10 eq 9 3 8
11 11 bad 10
```

Listing 2.1: BTOR2 example

The example circuit in Listing 2.1 has the following elements:

Sorts (Types). At the beginning of the circuit, node 1 declares a bit-vector of width 3 `sort bitvec 3`, which serves as the type for all 3-bit values used throughout the circuit. This will have a sort id or `sid` of 1 which will be used to declare registers and operations.

Constants. Node 2 defines a constant `zero 1`, which produces the bit-vector 000. Following this, node 3 introduces a state variable of sort 1 (3 bits), representing the main state of the circuit.

States. The initial value of state 3 is specified in node 4, which uses the `init` keyword to bind state 3 to start at constant 2, which is the 000 bit-vector. The next input is defined in node 5 using `one 1`, which denotes the constant 001.

Operations. Node 6 defines an addition operation that adds 1 to the main state, resulting in node 6, the next value of the counter. This operation wraps around on overflow due to the fixed 3-bit width. Line 7 then uses the `next` keyword to specify that in the next state, the counter should take the value of node 6, i.e., the incremented result.

Safety Properties. To define a property of interest, node 8 declares another constant: `ones 1`, which represents the maximum value a 3-bit counter can hold, in this case 111. Node 9 introduces a new sort of width 1, which is used for boolean-like signals such as equality checks.

Comparison. Node 10 defines a comparison between the current counter value and the maximum value 111 using the `eq` operator. This operation returns a 1-bit result: true (1) if the counter is at maximum, false (0) otherwise. Finally, node 11 marks this equality result as a bad state, which is a safety property violation. Hence, the circuit asserts that reaching the value 111 is undesirable or erroneous.

In summary, this BTOR2 circuit models a 3-bit counter that increments with each step and triggers a bad state when it reaches 111. This design could be used in formal verification to

¹<https://github.com/Boolector/btor2tools/tree/b8456dda4780789e882f5791eb486f295ade4da4/examples/btorsim> The example is taken from the official BTOR2 repository. The file is named `count2` to distinguish it from the corresponding `count.btor` example used in the previous BTOR format.

Figure 2.2: Comparison of hardware and software model checking toolchains, distinguishing between direct hardware analysis and indirect translation to C.

prove that the system avoids overflow, or alternatively, to find the point at which it does. The clear structure and modular nature of BTOR2 make it suitable for such sequential hardware modeling and property checking.

2.4 Bridging the Gap: Software Verification Algorithms in Hardware Flows

To leverage the advanced capabilities of modern software verification tools, hardware verification often employs an *indirect transformation* strategy. In this workflow, hardware descriptions (such as BTOR2) are translated into a software language, typically C, enabling the use of a broad array of software analyzers [8]. The primary motivation for this approach is that the software verification domain has evolved techniques not always available in hardware solvers. Research has demonstrated that by translating hardware models to software, software model checkers can reveal bugs that elude even state-of-the-art hardware analyzers (such as ABC or AVR) and, in some instances, perform more than an order of magnitude faster. [27]

Figure 2.2 illustrates the distinction between these verification toolchains. In traditional hardware flows (left), design-level hardware description languages like Verilog – which can contain ambiguities – are transformed into intermediate representations (IRs) such as AIGER or BTOR2, supported by more verification tools. These IRs are then fed into hardware analyzers.

In contrast, the software-centric approach (right) introduces an additional translation step to C. This creates a dichotomy in verification methodologies:

Direct Transformations: The analyzer natively accepts the input model (e.g., a hardware analyzer reading AIGER, or a software analyzer reading C source code).

Indirect Transformations: The model undergoes a domain translation (e.g., BTOR2 to C) to bridge the gap between hardware semantics and software verification algorithms.

The ecosystem surrounding these transformations relies on several specialized tools shown in Figure 2.2. **Yosys** [34] serves as a fundamental open-source framework for hardware

synthesis, often responsible for generating the initial intermediate representations. Tools such as **v2c** [28] and **Btor2Aiger** [29] facilitate the translation between various hardware formats (like Verilog and AIGER). Most critical to the software-centric workflow described in this thesis is **Btor2C** [8], which translates BTOR2 circuits into sequential C programs, thereby unlocking the potential of software model checking for hardware verification.

2.5 The Theta Framework and C Verification

The Theta framework [33, 2] serves as the foundation for this work, providing a modular, extensible platform for model checking. Theta employs abstraction-refinement-based reachability analysis and supports multiple formalisms through its frontend architecture. The framework’s existing C frontend, to which we will refer as C2CFA in this work, transforms C programs into a Control-Flow Automaton (CFA), which extends the traditional CFA model with additional constructs such as function calls, thread creation, and synchronization primitives. This richer representation enables the analysis of more complex program behaviors while preserving a unified intermediate form on which different verification algorithms can operate. Theta’s support for CEGAR (Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement) [31] and configurable abstract domains makes it particularly suitable for adapting to various verification domains.

Chapter 3

BTOR2CFA: Implementation of a Direct BTOR2-to-CFA Translation for Verification

In Section 3.1, I discuss the motivation behind this work. Next, Section 3.2 describes in detail the transformation implemented within Theta and presents illustrative examples. Finally, Section 3.3 explains the approach used to compare the direct and indirect transformations.

3.1 Motivation

Btor2C. As discussed in previous chapters, numerous approaches have been proposed to verify hardware circuits using software analyzers. One notable example is *Btor2C* [8], a tool originally conceived as a universal translator to convert hardware descriptions into C programs compatible with any standard software verifier. To achieve this universality while preserving precise hardware semantics, the generated C code often relies on abstract representations and indirections, particularly when modeling bitvector operations. This translation bridges the gap between hardware and software verification by enabling the use of existing C verification tools. In contrast, my work focuses on implementing a dedicated hardware frontend directly within an existing software model checker, eliminating the need for translation into C and its associated overhead.

Problem Statement. Using C as an intermediate representation between BTOR2 and a formal model (in this case, a Control Flow Automaton, CFA) can introduce semantic discrepancies and reduce verification efficiency. This additional transformation layer may obscure the original hardware semantics and complicate the verification process. So far there was no unified tool in which both the direct and indirect transformation approaches can be compared fairly.

Figure 3.1 illustrates the difference between the two workflows. The indirect approach involves first translating the BTOR2 circuit into C code using BTOR2C, followed by converting the C code into a CFA representation for verification. In contrast, the direct approach implemented in this work transforms the BTOR2 circuit directly into a CFA, bypassing the intermediate C representation entirely.

Figure 3.1: Workflow of direct and indirect transformation in software verification.

Proposed solution. By implementing a BTOR2 frontend in THETA, a modular and extensible model checking framework, I aim to:

1. Eliminate the intermediate C translation step,
2. preserve native BTOR2 semantics through direct mapping to SMT solver types,
3. enable BTOR2-specific optimizations directly on the CFA representation,
4. provide a unified framework for both hardware and software verification

3.2 Design and Implementation of the BTOR2 Frontend in Theta

The implementation began with defining an unofficial BTOR2 grammar using ANTLR4 [30], a widely-adopted parser generator for constructing domain-specific languages. This grammar enables systematic parsing of BTOR2 circuits and extraction of circuit elements for transformation.

Control-Flow Automata (CFA) naturally represent sequential circuits through their directed graph structure. In Figure 3.2, I present a schematic overview of this representation and explain how each step corresponds to a specific node. The transformation from BTOR2 to CFA follows a systematic mapping, where:

Constants. The transformation begins by adding all constant nodes defined in the BTOR2 model (e.g., `const`, `zero`, `one`, `ones` etc.) to the initial CFA edge. These constants serve as fixed symbolic values throughout the verification process.

Initial states. The `init` keyword in BTOR2 specifies initialization functions for state variables. In the CFA representation, these are defined on the subsequent edge, establishing the initial state configuration of the system.

Havoc assignments. Nodes declared with the `input` keyword, or state variables without an associated `next` definition, are introduced after the initial state. These represent unconstrained inputs whose values may vary across different execution iterations.

Figure 3.2: Schematic overview of the BTOR2CFA transformation process.

Operations. Next, the transformation processes all operation nodes (add, and, eq, etc.) in topological order, sequentially creating corresponding CFA edges and locations for each operation to preserve the computational dependencies of the circuit.

Safety Properties. The bad keyword defines the reachability property for verification. The transformation models this as a conditional transition originating from the referenced operation node. If the bad condition is satisfied, the CFA branches to an error location; otherwise, the control flow proceeds to the next state update.

Next states. Finally, if the safety property is not violated, all state variables defined with the next keyword are updated accordingly, completing one iteration of the transition system.

This mapping enables Theta to perform exhaustive reachability analysis, exploring all possible execution paths to determine whether error states are reachable from initial configurations.

3.2.1 Example BTOR2 to CFA Transformation

Figure 3.3 illustrates the direct transformation from the count2.btor2 example to a simplified CFA. The BTOR2 circuit implements a 3-bit counter that increments each cycle and triggers a bad state when reaching the value 111.

The transformation process maps:

- The initial state assignment ($s_3 := 000$) from the init operation

Figure 3.3: Simplified CFA from the count2.btor2 example

- The increment operation ($n_6 := s_3 + 001$) as a computation edge
- The state update ($s_3 := n_6$) from the next operation
- The safety condition ($[s_3 = 111]$) from the bad property

The resulting CFA naturally captures the cyclic behavior of the hardware circuit as a graph loop, enabling efficient reachability analysis using Theta’s verification algorithms.

3.3 Comparison between Direct and Indirect Transformations

This section contrasts the direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation developed in this thesis against the traditional indirect workflow (via C). Implementing both approaches within the same verification framework (THETA) provides a solid foundation for a fair and consistent evaluation. By integrating both workflows into a single tool, differences in performance or accuracy can be attributed primarily to the transformation methodology itself, rather than to unrelated factors such as solver configurations or tool-specific heuristics.

3.3.1 Conceptual Differences

The fundamental distinction between the two approaches lies in their semantic fidelity to the original hardware description.

Direct Transformation (BTOR2CFA) The direct transformation approach establishes a one-to-one mapping from hardware circuits to formal verification models. Its primary goal is to preserve the native semantics of the hardware description without introducing unnecessary abstractions. By eliminating intermediate translation steps, this method maintains the structural integrity of the original circuit design and enables the exploitation of hardware-specific patterns – such as bit-level logic and synchronous state updates – that might otherwise be obscured.

Indirect Transformation (C2CFA) In contrast, indirect transformation approaches introduce additional abstraction layers. Translating hardware into software-oriented representations (like C) often results in conceptual mismatches, such as the disparity between hardware cycles and software loops. These discrepancies accumulate through successive translation steps, introducing artifacts that complicate the verification process.

To concretely illustrate these artifacts, Figure 3.4 presents a snippet of C code generated by BTOR2C for a simple counter circuit. Even for this trivial example, the translation introduces explicit type definitions, bit-masks (e.g., `mask_SORT_1`), and numerous auxiliary variables (e.g., `var_10_arg_0`) to emulate bit-vector semantics. This visually demonstrates how the indirect approach inflates structural complexity compared to the concise original hardware description.

```

extern void abort (void);
extern unsigned char nondet_uchar();

int main() {
1 sort bitvec 3      typedef unsigned char SORT_1; // BV with 3 bits
2 zero 1            const SORT_1 mask_SORT_1 = (SORT_1)-1 >> (sizeof(SORT_1) * 8 - 3);
3 state 1          const SORT_1 msb_SORT_1 = (SORT_1)1 << (3 - 1);
4 init 1 3 2       typedef unsigned char SORT_9; // BV with 1 bits
5 one 1           const SORT_9 mask_SORT_9 = (SORT_9)-1 >> (sizeof(SORT_9) * 8 - 1);
6 add 1 3 5        const SORT_9 msb_SORT_9 = (SORT_9)1 << (1 - 1);
7 next 1 3 6       const SORT_1 var_2 = 0;
8 ones 1          const SORT_1 var_5 = 1;
9 sort bitvec 1    const SORT_1 var_8 = mask_SORT_1;
10 eq 9 3 8        SORT_1 state_3 = nondet_uchar() & mask_SORT_1;
11 bad 10         SORT_1 init_4_arg_1 = var_2;
                  state_3 = init_4_arg_1;
                  for (;;) {
                    SORT_1 var_10_arg_0 = state_3;
                    SORT_1 var_10_arg_1 = var_8;
                    SORT_9 var_10 = var_10_arg_0 == var_10_arg_1;
                    SORT_9 bad_11_arg_0 = var_10;
                    __VERIFIER_assert(!(bad_11_arg_0));

                    SORT_1 var_6_arg_0 = state_3;
                    SORT_1 var_6_arg_1 = var_5;
                    SORT_1 var_6 = var_6_arg_0 + var_6_arg_1;
                    var_6 = var_6 & mask_SORT_1;
                    SORT_1 next_7_arg_1 = var_6;

                    state_3 = next_7_arg_1;
                  }
                  return 0;
}

```

Figure 3.4: `count2.btor2` example translated to C by BTOR2C (simplified version), illustrating the introduction of auxiliary masks and variables.

Table 3.1 summarizes these structural and semantic differences.

3.4 Implementation Considerations and Optimization Trade-offs

The choice of transformation pathway significantly influences the resulting model’s complexity and the subsequent performance of the model checker.

3.4.1 Theta’s C Frontend: A Mature but Complex Infrastructure

THETA’s existing C frontend is a highly optimized and robust component, refined over years to handle the complexities of software verification with high efficiency. It excels at processing standard C programs, accurately modeling memory safety, pointer arithmetic, and control flow.

However, when applied to hardware verification via the Btor2C workflow, its performance is impacted not by its own design, but by the nature of the input it receives:

Table 3.1: Conceptual comparison of BTOR2 (Simple) and C (Complex) frontends

Category	BTOR2CFA (Direct)	C2CFA (Indirect)
Variable dependencies	Straightforward variable relations mirroring the netlist.	Introduction of numerous auxiliary variables for function calls and scope management.
Temporary variables	Minimal use of temporary variables.	Extensive use of temporary variables for parameter passing and value copying.
State handling	State is updated directly via next-state logic.	State is modified indirectly through function calls, pointers, and parameters.
Bit-level operations	Bit-widths are handled natively and automatically.	Bit-widths must be enforced manually using explicit masking operations.
Control Structure	Encapsulated in a single, simple procedure.	Fragmented across several procedures, incurring call overhead.
Instrumentation	Minimal additional logic required.	Complex logic introduced to enforce C semantics and assertion checks.

- **Inherited Structural Complexity:** The structural overhead observed in the C workflow is primarily an artifact of the BTOR2C translation tool, not the frontend itself. To simulate hardware parallelism and bit-vector semantics within the sequential C language, BTOR2C must generate explicit bit-masks, temporary variables, and auxiliary assignments. The C frontend faithfully models this verbose input, resulting in a bloated CFA that accurately reflects the C code but obscures the original, concise hardware logic.
- **Semantic Mismatch:** The C frontend is designed to analyze software idioms. When hardware logic is emulated using C constructs (e.g., modeling cyclic state updates via function calls or loops), the frontend processes them as standard software control flow. This emulation acts as an optimization barrier, as the underlying solver must reason about the complex emulation logic rather than the simple bit-vector transitions of the original circuit.

3.4.2 BTOR2 Frontend: Minimalist and Domain-Specific

In contrast, the BTOR2 frontend was implemented to leverage the foundational concepts of the THETA framework while adhering strictly to standard SMT-LIB semantics. By utilizing THETA’s existing type system and expression hierarchy, the direct transformation ensures rigorous formal verification standards and compatibility with downstream SMT solvers.

Key design advantages include:

- **Direct Mapping:** Bit-vector types map directly to SMT solver types, preserving precise semantics without intermediate representation.

- **Graph-Based Loops:** Cyclic behavior is naturally expressed as CFA loops, avoiding the need for the explicit unrolling or simulation constructs often found in C translations.
- **Targeted Optimizations:** Domain-specific optimizations, such as Large-Block Encoding and variable elimination, can be applied directly to the CFA. This reduces redundancy and improves solver performance by presenting a cleaner state space.

3.5 Limitations of the Current Implementation

While the direct transformation offers significant advantages, the current implementation has specific limitations regarding applicability and feature support:

- **Incomplete Language Support:** The frontend currently limits the scope of verifiable circuits due to two primary gaps in the BTOR2 specification coverage:
 - *Missing Operators:* Specific arithmetic and bit-manipulation operators, such as overflow predicates (e.g., `saddo`, `uaddo`) and reduction operations (e.g., `redand`, `redor`), are not yet implemented.
 - *Lack of Array Support:* The tool currently provides no support for the BTOR2 array sort or associated array operations (e.g., `read`, `write`), preventing the verification of designs that rely on memory modeling.
- **No Witness Generation:** The tool does not yet generate counterexamples or witness files. This hinders integration into formal verification competitions (like SV-COMP) and industrial workflows that require actionable feedback for debugging.
- **Limited Property Scope:** Verification is currently restricted to safety properties (bad states). Liveness properties (e.g., `justice`, `fairness`) and other temporal specifications remain unsupported.

Chapter 4

Evaluation

This chapter presents a comprehensive evaluation of the BTOR2CFA transformation approach, contrasting it with the traditional translation-based workflow utilizing BTOR2C. The experimental methodology and benchmark selection are detailed in Section 4.1. Subsequent sections analyze the structural complexity of the generated models (Section 4.2), evaluate the comparative performance of various model checking algorithms (Section 4.3), investigate the relationship between structural complexity and verification performance (Section 4.4), and assess the impact of optimization within the transformation pipeline (Section 4.5). A summary of the key findings and a discussion of threats to validity conclude the chapter in Section 4.6.

4.1 Experiment Design

This section details the experimental methodology employed to ensure a rigorous comparison. It outlines the hardware and software environment, defines the specific research questions addressing the evaluation goals, and describes the criteria used to curate the benchmark suite.

4.1.1 Research Questions

The evaluation aims to answer the following research questions:

- RQ1:** How does the structural complexity of the CFAs differ between direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation and the Btor2C translation approach?
- RQ2:** Which model checking algorithms perform best for hardware verification, and how does input type (BTOR2 vs C) affect performance?
- RQ3:** How does the structural complexity of the CFAs impact verification efficiency?
- RQ4:** How does optimization of BTOR2CFA transformations impact verification efficiency?

4.1.2 Benchmark Suite and Methodology

The Hardware Model Checking Competition (HWMCC) [12] provides a comprehensive suite of state-of-the-art benchmark models for evaluating hardware verification tools. In this work, I used a subset of these benchmarks selected according to the following criteria.

First, since my implementation focuses exclusively on safety property verification, only benchmarks containing the bad property were considered. Benchmarks featuring liveness-related properties (such as justice, fair, output, and constraint) were excluded from the evaluation.

Secondly, as the current implementation of Theta (and consequently BTOR2CFA) does not support overflow predicate or reduce operations, benchmarks utilizing these features were excluded to ensure compatibility.

After applying these filtering criteria, a total of 698 benchmarks remained. The evaluation utilized both the BTOR2 and C benchmark subsets provided by HWMCC.

Evaluation Workflows To rigorously compare the efficiency of the proposed solution against the state-of-the-art, each circuit was processed through two distinct transformation workflows:

1. **Direct Approach (BTOR2CFA):** The BTOR2 files were parsed and transformed directly into THETA’s native Control-Flow Automata (CFA) using the frontend developed in this thesis. This approach bypasses all external translation steps.
2. **Indirect Approach (C2CFA):** The BTOR2 files were first translated into C source code using the external BTOR2C tool [8]. These generated C programs were then parsed by THETA’s existing C frontend to produce the final CFA.

The evaluation was conducted in two phases. First, a **Structural Analysis** was performed where only the transformation to CFA was executed to compare graph metrics (nodes, edges, variables) without running the verification algorithms. Second, a **Performance Analysis** was conducted where full verification cycles were executed using various model checking algorithms to measure solving time and memory consumption on the generated models.

CFA Analysis Several metrics of the Control-Flow Automata (CFAs) generated during the transformation process were systematically compared. This evaluation quantified the number of variables, locations, edges, and operations. To ensure a valid direct comparison, the dataset was filtered to include only the intersection of instances successfully processed by both workflows. Consequently, if a benchmark resulted in a timeout or memory exhaustion in either the C2CFA or BTOR2CFA path, it was excluded from the structural analysis. The remaining 551 benchmark pairs provided a robust and representative basis for this comparative study. Notably, the BTOR2CFA workflow successfully processed every instance that was solvable by the C implementation.

Performance Analysis For the performance evaluation, I compared several verification algorithms supported by THETA. Specifically, I tested Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement (CEGAR) [31] with both explicit-value and predicate abstraction, as well as Bounded Model Checking (BMC) [9], k -Induction [32], and Interpolation-Based Model Checking (IMC) [26].

	BTOR2CFA		C2CFA	
	Avg	Median	Avg	Median
Variables	1153.93	928.0	3241.07	2561.0
Locations	3.00	3.0	5.00	5.0
Edges	3.00	3.0	4.00	4.0
Statements	1321.20	1068.0	7543.92	6025.0

Table 4.1: Average and median CFA metrics for both workflows.

4.1.2.1 Measurement Procedure

All experiments were conducted on virtual machines equipped with Intel Xeon (Skylake) processors, featuring between 2 and 32 cores operating at 2.2 GHz, and memory configurations ranging from 16 GB to 128 GB of RAM. The operating system used was Linux 6.8.0-60-generic, and all experiments were performed using THETA version 6.27.12. For SMT solving, I employed MATHSAT version 5.6.10 [17].

To ensure reliable and reproducible performance measurements, I utilized the RUNEXEC tool from the BENCHEXEC¹ suite [7], a state-of-the-art benchmarking framework also used in the SV-COMP competition. Each experiment was executed with a CPU time limit of 900 seconds, a memory limit of 15 GB, and restricted to two CPU cores.

4.2 Structural Complexity Analysis

This section investigates the differences in structural complexity between the CFAs generated by the direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation and those produced by the indirect Btor2C translation approach. The comparative analysis reveals that the direct translation yields a significantly more concise intermediate representation, as illustrated in Figure 4.1 and Table 4.1.

Complexity Overhead in C Parsing Figure 4.1 demonstrates the relationship between the number of atomic statements and variables across the two formats. The data points cluster well below the $x = y$ diagonal (where x is C), indicating that the high-level C parsing generates a substantially larger number of atomic statements. This is likely due to the introduction of intermediate auxiliary variables and the explicit unrolling of high-level constructs during the translation from C to the CFA intermediate language. Quantitative data presented in Table 4.1 reveals that the direct transformation *reduces* the variable count to approximately *one-third* of that observed in the indirect approach. In contrast, the indirect transformation exhibits a *six-fold increase* in the number of atomic statements.

As illustrated in Figure 4.1, the edge and location counts exhibit a high degree of convergence between the two formats, resulting in negligible ratio differences. This structural similarity is a direct consequence of the optimization pass applied in both workflows – specifically (sequential) Large-Block Encoding (LBE) [6] – which effectively compresses sequences of edges into a single edge with several statements. Consequently, edge and location counts lack discriminative power in this context and are therefore excluded from subsequent complexity analyses.

¹<https://github.com/sosy-lab/benchexec>

Structural Comparison: C2CFA vs BTOR2CFA (Task by Task)

Figure 4.1: Comparison of number of statements showing the scale of complexity expansion between C2CFA and BTOR2CFA transformations.

Dataset	CPU Time (s)			Memory (MB)			Success (%)
	Avg	Median	SD	Avg	Median	SD	
C2CFA	141.02	54.89	148.83	1878.00	984.34	2120.07	75.43
BTOR2CFA	22.42	10.46	48.93	461.02	316.43	338.16	98.71

Table 4.2: Summary of CPU time, memory usage, and success rate for the C2CFA and BTOR2CFA transformations.

The structural expansion within the C format is a direct consequence of the artifacts introduced during the translation from parallel hardware descriptions to sequential C code. Whereas BTOR2CFA efficiently encodes state utilizing compact bit-vector arrays, the C frontend explicitly instantiates distinct variables for intermediate calculations and memory addressing. Consequently, the BTOR2 format provides a significantly more concise representation for verification tasks within this context.

These structural disparities directly correlate with the performance metrics presented in Table 4.2. The C2CFA transformation incurs a substantially higher computational overhead in terms of both memory footprint and CPU time. This increased resource consumption provides a clear rationale for the elevated frequency of timeouts and out-of-memory exceptions observed in the indirect approach.

4.2.1 RQ1: How does the structural complexity differ between direct BTOR2CFA transformation and the Btor2C translation approach?

The experimental results demonstrate a fundamental structural disparity between the two approaches. The direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation generates a significantly more concise intermediate representation compared to the Btor2C translation. The findings from the structural analysis reveal that the indirect C-based workflow results in approximately a **three-fold increase in variable count** and a **six-fold increase in atomic statements**.

This “structural expansion” in the C workflow is attributed to the semantic mismatch between the high-level C language and low-level hardware logic. The C frontend introduces numerous auxiliary variables and explicit operations to emulate memory addressing and scope, whereas the direct transformation effectively maps hardware bit-vectors to the CFA’s internal representation without such overhead.

4.3 Algorithm Performance Analysis

This section evaluates which model checking algorithms perform best for hardware verification and assesses the impact of input type (BTOR2 vs C) on their performance. The performance evaluation across different model checking algorithms reveals clear advantages for the direct BTOR2 transformation approach. Tables 4.3 and 4.4 summarize the CPU time, memory usage, and success rates for algorithms using BTOR2 and C inputs respectively.

Figure 4.2 presents the quantile plots for CPU time and memory usage across all verified configurations. The results unequivocally demonstrate the superiority of the direct

Figure 4.2: Quantile plots comparing the CPU time (left) and memory usage (right) of different model checking algorithms. The plots display the cumulative number of solved instances (x-axis) against the resources consumed (logarithmic y-axis) for both BTOR2 and C benchmark sets. Algorithms include CEGAR (Predictive and Explicit), BMC, IMC, and k -Induction.

BTOR2-to-CFA transformation (represented by dashed lines) over the indirect C-based workflow (solid lines).

4.3.1 Analysis of Solved Instances and Resource Consumption

The quantile plots presented in Figure 4.2 provide a comprehensive overview of the performance differences between the two transformation workflows. In these plots, the x-axis represents the cumulative number of solved instances, while the y-axis (logarithmic scale) indicates the resource consumption (CPU time and memory) required to solve the n -th instance.

4.3.1.1 Workflow Comparison

The most prominent observation is the consistent superiority of the direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation (represented by dashed lines) over the indirect translation via C (solid lines). Across all five verifying algorithms (CEGAR with explicit-value and predicative abstraction, BMC, IMC, and k -Induction) the direct approach significantly outperforms the indirect approach in terms of total solved instances. The solid curves exhibit a much steeper ascent, indicating that the C-based workflow exhausts resources rapidly even on

instances that are computationally trivial for the direct approach. This “brick wall” effect confirms the hypothesis that the structural overhead introduced by the C frontend creates a baseline complexity that hinders scalability.

4.3.1.2 Algorithmic Effectiveness and Resource Consumption

Regarding algorithmic performance, Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement with Predicate Abstraction (CEGAR_PRED) utilizing the direct BTOR2 input emerges as the unequivocally most robust configuration. As detailed in Table 4.3, it achieves the highest success rate of **16.62%**, significantly outperforming the next best algorithm, *k*-Induction (8.74%). This confirms that predicate abstraction is particularly well-suited for handling the bit-level logic inherent in hardware designs, effectively balancing precision and abstraction.

In terms of resource efficiency, CEGAR_PRED on BTOR2 maintains a sustainable footprint. It exhibits a median CPU time of 51.99 s and a median memory usage of 859.59 MB. Although the standard deviation for memory (1859.61 MB) indicates variability across difficult instances, it remains far more efficient than its performance on the C input.

Impact of Input Format on Performance Comparing Table 4.3 and Table 4.4 reveals the severe performance penalty introduced by the C translation workflow. For the CEGAR_PRED configuration, switching from BTOR2 to C causes the success rate to plummet from 16.62% to **5.03%**. Furthermore, the resource consumption increases drastically:

- **Memory Inflation:** The median memory usage for CEGAR_PRED nearly quadruples, rising from 859.59 MB (BTOR2) to 2990.98 MB (C). Similarly, IMC sees its median memory usage jump from 750.75 MB to 3085.55 MB.
- **Computational Effort:** The median CPU time for CEGAR_PRED increases from 51.99 s to 129.78 s, indicating that the solver struggles significantly more to reach a conclusion on the C-generated CFAs.

The Explicit Value Anomaly The CEGAR_EXPL (Explicit Value Analysis) configuration presents a notable statistical anomaly. As shown in both tables, it reports the lowest average CPU times (e.g., 19.92 s for BTOR2) and memory footprints. However, this should not be interpreted as efficiency. With the lowest success rates in the suite (3.58% for BTOR2 and a negligible 1.01% for C), these low resource metrics indicate that the algorithm fails rapidly on non-trivial instances, managing to solve only the simplest benchmarks before quickly exhausting its search capabilities or timing out.

4.3.2 RQ2: Which model checking algorithms perform best for hardware verification, and how does input type (Btor2 vs C) affect performance?

Best Algorithm Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement with Predicate Abstraction (CEGAR_PRED) utilizing the direct BTOR2 input is unequivocally the most effective configuration. It achieved the highest success rate (16.62%) and demonstrated the best scalability, solving approximately 115 instances while maintaining moderate resource consumption.

Table 4.3: Summary of CPU time, memory usage, and success rate for algorithms using BTOR2 as input.

Algorithm	CPU Time (s)			Memory (MB)			Success (%)
	Avg	Median	SD	Avg	Median	SD	
BMC	182.13	61.60	252.35	696.40	649.18	384.88	7.16
CEGAR_EXPL	19.92	14.47	13.43	480.98	405.40	295.37	3.58
CEGAR_PRED	134.67	51.99	172.61	1717.04	859.59	1859.61	16.62
IMC	159.21	52.98	216.72	1060.91	750.75	890.43	7.31
<i>k</i> -Induction	178.39	56.57	256.25	777.55	673.83	502.48	8.74

Table 4.4: Summary of CPU time, memory usage, and success rate for algorithms using C as input.

Algorithm	CPU Time (s)			Memory (MB)			Success (%)
	Avg	Median	SD	Avg	Median	SD	
BMC	171.63	23.76	277.89	1070.70	304.83	1892.30	1.01
CEGAR_EXPL	232.52	11.53	351.92	1696.30	297.23	2270.82	1.01
CEGAR_PRED	270.11	129.78	259.44	4176.83	2990.98	3436.76	5.03
IMC	283.48	149.17	267.46	3314.08	3085.55	3201.35	1.87
<i>k</i> -Induction	187.27	49.03	268.60	2506.06	2686.79	2145.25	2.59

Transformation Impact Based on my research, the choice of workflow is a decisive factor in verification performance. The C2CFA input induces a severe performance penalty across all tested algorithms.

Resource Exhaustion. The “brick wall” effect observed in the quantile plots (Figure 4.2) indicates that C-generated models cause rapid resource exhaustion. For CEGAR_PRED, switching to C input quadrupled the median memory usage (from ≈ 860 MB to ≈ 2990 MB).

Algorithmic degradation. Explicit Value Analysis (CEGAR_EXPL), which struggles generally with hardware logic, fails almost entirely when processing C inputs (1.01% success rate), confirming that the added structural complexity exacerbates the weaknesses of less robust algorithms.

4.4 Analysis of Structural Complexity and Performance

This section examines the impact of structural complexity on verification efficiency. To better understand the root causes of the performance disparities observed in Figure 4.2, I analyzed the Pearson correlation coefficients between structural metrics (Variable Count, Atomic Statements) and performance indicators (CPU Time, Memory). The resulting correlation matrices for the BTOR2 and C workflows are presented in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4, respectively.

Decoupling of Size and Difficulty in Direct Transformation The correlation matrices for the BTOR2 input (Figure 4.3) reveal a significant insight: there is a remarkably weak correlation between the structural size of the CFA and the computational resources

required to verify it. For instance, in the CEGAR_PRED configuration, the correlation between Variable Count and CPU Time is only 0.27. Even more notably, for Bounded Model Checking (BMC), this correlation drops to -0.13 . This suggests that for the direct transformation, the verification complexity is driven primarily by the logical depth and semantic properties of the circuit, rather than the raw size of the state space representation. The solver is effectively able to abstract away the structural components.

Structural Dependency in Indirect Translation In stark contrast, the correlation matrices for the C input (Figure 4.4) demonstrate a strong positive correlation between structural metrics and resource consumption across almost all algorithms. For the BMC algorithm, the correlation between Variable Count and CPU Time rises to 0.82. Similarly, CEGAR_EXPL shows a correlation of 0.82 for the same metric. This indicates a strong coupling between structure and performance: the “structural expansion” introduced by the C frontend (discussed in Section 4.2) creates a linear – and often prohibitive – performance penalty. Every additional auxiliary variable or split operation introduced during C parsing directly increases the burden on the solver.

Impact on Memory Scalability The impact of this structural coupling is visible in the memory correlations. In the C workflow, Memory usage correlates strongly with Variable Count (e.g., 0.88 for BMC). In the BTOR2 workflow, this correlation is significantly weaker (0.48 for BMC). This confirms that the memory exhaustion observed in the quantile plots is largely a function of the inefficient intermediate representation generated by the C frontend, which forces the model checker to track a vastly larger set of state variables than is theoretically necessary.

4.4.1 RQ3: How does the structural complexity of the CFAs impact verification efficiency?

My correlation analysis reveals two distinct behaviors regarding structural complexity and efficiency:

Decoupling in Direct Transformation. For the direct workflow, there is a negligible correlation (e.g., $r \approx -0.13$ for BMC) between the size of the model (variable count) and verification time. This indicates that the direct transformation preserves the logical semantics clearly enough that solvers can abstract away structural size, making performance dependent on *logical* depth rather than *structural* breadth.

Strong Coupling in Indirect Translation. Conversely, the C workflow exhibits a strong positive correlation ($r > 0.8$) between variable count and resource usage. The extraneous complexity introduced by the C frontend creates a burden that the solver cannot optimize away, leading to a linear dependency where “larger” CFAs invariably result in slower verification and higher memory footprints.

4.5 Impact of Optimization on Verification Efficiency

This section investigates the impact of optimization on verification efficiency within the BTOR2CFA pipeline. To address **RQ4**, I evaluated the performance impact of the optimization passes within the BTOR2CFA transformation pipeline. Figure 4.5 presents a

Correlation Matrices - Input Type: BTOR2

Figure 4.3: Feature correlation heatmaps for BTOR2 inputs. The subplots compare the internal dependencies of problem variables and their correlation with runtime and memory usage for BMC, CEGAR (Explicit/Predictive), IMC, and k -Induction configurations.

Correlation Matrices - Input Type: C

Figure 4.4: Feature correlation heatmaps for C inputs. The subplots compare the internal dependencies of problem variables and their correlation with runtime and memory usage for BMC, CEGAR (Explicit/Predictive), IMC, and k -Induction configurations.

Figure 4.5: Quantile plots comparing the CPU time (left) and memory usage (right) of different model checking algorithms. The plots display the cumulative number of solved instances (x-axis) against the resources consumed (logarithmic y-axis) for both optimized BTOR2CFA and unoptimized transformations. Algorithms include CEGAR (Predictive and Explicit), BMC, IMC, and k -Induction.

comparative quantile plot of the BTOR2-based workflow with and without optimization enabled.

The results unequivocally demonstrate that optimization is a critical factor for verification viability. The unoptimized configurations (represented by dashed lines) exhibit a severe performance degradation across all algorithms.

- **CEGAR_PRED:** The optimized configuration (solid blue line) successfully solves approximately 115 instances. In stark contrast, the unoptimized version (dashed orange line) reaches its limit after solving only roughly 25 instances.
- **BMC and k -Induction:** The disparity is even more pronounced for Bounded Model Checking and k -Induction. Without optimization, these algorithms fail to solve more than 10 instances, appearing as near-vertical lines on the far left of the plot.

This massive performance gap suggests that the raw, direct translation from BTOR2 to CFA produces a highly redundant control-flow graph. Without the reduction techniques (such as Large-Block Encoding and variable elimination) applied during the optimization phase, the resulting state space is unnecessarily bloated, overwhelming the underlying solvers regardless of the model checking algorithm employed.

4.5.1 RQ4: How does optimization of BTOR2CFA transformations impact verification efficiency?

Optimization is identified not merely as an enhancement, but as a **prerequisite for viability** in the BTOR2 verification pipeline. The comparative analysis shows a drastic divergence in performance:

Unoptimized. Without optimization passes (such as Large-Block Encoding), algorithms saturate rapidly, with the best configuration solving fewer than 30 instances. The raw CFA generation produces a state space too redundant for efficient traversal.

Optimized. Enabling optimizations allows the solver to handle significantly more complex designs, increasing the solved instance count from ≈ 25 to ≈ 115 for CEGAR_PRED.

Therefore, structural reduction techniques are essential to bridge the gap between the raw translation of hardware circuits and the input requirements of efficient model checking algorithms. Notably, the unoptimized BTOR2CFA workflow exhibits performance characteristics that are remarkably similar to those of the C2CFA approach.

4.6 Summary of Results

This work presented BTOR2CFA, a direct transformation from the BTOR2 hardware description format to Control-Flow Automata (CFA) within the Theta model checking framework. The primary goal was to eliminate the intermediate C translation step introduced by tools like Btor2C, thereby creating a more efficient and semantically precise verification workflow for hardware circuits.

The comparative evaluation yielded clear and significant results. The direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation consistently produced dramatically more compact and less complex models than the translation-based approach. Key findings include:

Structural Superiority

The direct transformation reduced variable counts by approximately 66% and atomic statements by about 82% compared to the indirect C-based approach.

Verification Efficiency

Across all evaluated algorithms, the direct approach achieved the highest success rate of 16.62%, significantly outperforming the indirect approach’s best 5.03%. Resource consumption was also drastically lower, with median memory usage reduced from 984 MB to 316 MB.

Algorithmic Performance

CEGAR with predicate abstraction (CEGAR_PRED) emerged as the most effective algorithm for BTOR2 verification, achieving a 16.62% success rate on the direct transformation, compared to only 5.03% on the indirect approach.

Optimization Impact

The optimization passes within BTOR2CFA were shown to be essential for verification viability, enabling the solution of over 115 instances compared to fewer than 30 without optimization.

These results demonstrate that eliminating the intermediate C translation step not only preserves hardware semantics more accurately but also enables significant performance gains in both scalability and resource efficiency.

4.6.1 Threats to Validity

This section outlines potential limitations that may influence the interpretation and reliability of the experimental results. These threats are categorized into internal validity, regarding the integrity of the study’s design, and external validity, concerning the generalizability of the findings.

4.6.1.1 Internal Validity

Several factors could affect the internal validity of this study:

- **Benchmark Selection:** The evaluation focused on safety property benchmarks from HWMCC, excluding liveness and other property types. This may limit the generalizability of the results to other verification contexts.
- **Tool Versioning:** The experiments were conducted with specific versions of THETA (6.27.12)² and MATHSAT (5.6.10). Changes in these tools could influence performance outcomes.
- **Configuration Consistency:** While RunExec was used to ensure consistent execution environments, subtle differences in virtual machine allocation or background processes could introduce minor variations in timing and memory measurements.

4.6.1.2 External Validity

The external validity of the study is influenced by:

- **Limited Operator Support:** The current implementation does not support all BTOR2 operators (e.g., reduce operations, overflow predicates, array operations). This restricts the evaluation to a subset of hardware circuits, potentially overlooking performance characteristics in more complex designs.
- **Hardware-Specific Benchmarks:** The study relied exclusively on HWMCC benchmarks, which may not fully represent industrial hardware verification scenarios or emerging circuit designs.
- **Algorithm Scope:** Only a subset of Theta’s verification algorithms was evaluated. Other algorithms or configurations might yield different performance trade-offs. It is important to acknowledge that THETA offers extensive configuration capabilities for each algorithm. Consequently, a comprehensive analysis of every possible parameter permutation would result in a combinatorial explosion, rendering such an exhaustive evaluation computationally infeasible.

²<https://github.com/ftsrg/theta>

Chapter 5

Related work

5.1 Related work

5.1.1 Btor2C and Translation-Based Workflows

As discussed in this work, numerous translation-based workflows exist, with Btor2C [8] being the most notable example. The authors of Btor2C investigated a fundamental architectural question: is it more effective to employ a universal translation tool to bridge hardware and software model checking, or is it more advantageous to extend individual software analyzers with dedicated hardware-specific frontends? This critical inquiry served as a primary inspiration for the research presented in this thesis.

Btor2C represents the state-of-the-art in hardware-to-software translation for verification purposes. The tool systematically converts BTOR2 circuits into C programs, enabling software verification tools to analyze hardware designs indirectly. This workflow facilitates the application of sophisticated software verification techniques – such as those found in CPACHECKER [4] and ESBMC [21] – to hardware circuits. Empirical results have demonstrated that this approach can uncover bugs that dedicated hardware verifiers like ABC [14] and AVR [22] miss under identical time constraints.

However, the Btor2C approach introduces a multi-step translation process: BTOR2 \rightarrow C \rightarrow CFA \rightarrow verification. Each transformation step potentially introduces semantic discrepancies and creates barriers to optimization. Furthermore, the translation must bridge fundamental differences between hardware and software paradigms, particularly regarding arbitrary-width bit-vector types and the representation of cyclic behavior.

5.1.2 Comparative Analysis of Verification Workflows

Verification workflows for hardware systems fall into two principal approaches with distinct trade-offs. Despite the advantages of each, detailed comparative analyses are scarce. The following discussion outlines the specific benefits and drawbacks associated with these workflows.

5.1.2.1 Direct Hardware Verification

The direct hardware verification paradigm utilizes specialized engines, such as **ABC** and **AVR**, which ingest and process hardware description formats natively. This methodol-

ogy adheres to a streamlined verification trajectory: BTOR2 \rightarrow direct verification. The distinct advantage of this approach is its preservation of native hardware semantics and bit-level abstractions, allowing for optimizations specifically tailored to circuit logic and state-space traversal. However, this specialization can also be a limitation; by operating in isolation, direct hardware verifiers may fail to capitalize on the rapid algorithmic advancements and heuristic innovations emerging from the broader software verification community.

5.1.2.2 Translation-Based Verification

Translation-based verification constitutes a hybrid paradigm designed to bridge the gap between hardware models and software analysis techniques. This workflow employs tools such as **Btor2C** in conjunction with software verifiers, executing a multi-stage transformation process: BTOR2 \rightarrow C \rightarrow CFA \rightarrow verification. The primary strength of this approach lies in its capacity to harness the mature ecosystem of software verification, granting access to sophisticated techniques – including advanced abstract interpretation, lazy abstraction, and diverse model checking algorithms – that are often absent in dedicated hardware tools. Conversely, the requisite translation introduces a semantic impedance mismatch. The conversion from hardware concurrency to software sequentiality can create optimization barriers and semantic gaps, potentially degrading verification efficiency and accuracy.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This thesis detailed the design, implementation, and evaluation of a direct BTOR2-to-CFA transformation within the Theta model checking framework. The work was motivated by the inefficiencies and potential semantic discrepancies introduced by existing translation-based workflows that convert hardware models to C code before verification.

The implemented BTOR2CFA frontend successfully demonstrates that a direct approach is not only feasible but also structurally and algorithmically superior. The evaluation conclusively shows that:

1. The direct transformation produces significantly more compact CFAs, reducing variable counts by two-thirds and statement counts by over 80%.
2. Verification performance is dramatically improved, with higher success rates, lower memory usage, and faster execution times across all tested algorithms.
3. Optimization passes are essential for scalability, enabling the verification of complex circuits that would otherwise be intractable.
4. The direct approach better preserves hardware semantics, enabling more accurate and efficient verification compared to indirect translation via C.

These findings validate the hypothesis that eliminating intermediate translation steps in hardware verification workflows can lead to substantial gains in both performance and semantic precision.

6.1 Future Work

The development of the BTOR2 frontend opens several avenues for future work to enhance its capabilities, robustness, and performance.

1. **Language Completeness:** The highest priority is to achieve full BTOR2 compliance. This involves:
 - Implementing support for unsupported operators, such as overflow-detecting arithmetic predicates (`saddo`, `uaddo`, etc.).
 - Adding support for array operations, which is crucial for modeling memory and other complex hardware components.

2. **Extended Property Verification:** Implementing the translation of BTOR2 liveness properties into Theta's formalism would significantly expand the frontend's applicability, allowing it to verify a broader class of hardware specifications.
3. **Algorithm Optimization:** Based on the performance results, further optimization of CEGAR_EXPL and CEGAR_PRED algorithms specifically for BTOR2 inputs could yield additional performance improvements.
4. **Witness Generation:** To become competitive in formal verification competitions like HWMCC, the tool must be able to generate witnesses (counterexamples or proofs). Integrating witness generation for both valid and invalid properties is an essential next step.
5. **Comprehensive Benchmarking and Debugging:** As the frontend matures, more extensive benchmarking on a broader array of circuits, including those using newly implemented features, is necessary to evaluate its robustness, correctness, and performance relative to state-of-the-art hardware verifiers like ABC and AVR.

With these improvements, the BTOR2 frontend for THETA has the potential to evolve into a competitive, comprehensive, and high-performance solution for hardware model checking.

Bibliography

- [1] Christel Baier and Joost-Pieter Katoen. *Principles of model checking*. MIT press, 2008.
- [2] Levente Bajczi, Zsófia Ádám, and Vince Molnár. C for yourself: comparison of front-end techniques for formal verification. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM 10th International Conference on Formal Methods in Software Engineering*, pages 1–11, 2022.
- [3] Clark Barrett, Aaron Stump, Cesare Tinelli, et al. The smt-lib standard: Version 2.0. In *Proceedings of the 8th international workshop on satisfiability modulo theories (Edinburgh, UK)*, volume 13, page 14, 2010.
- [4] Dirk Beyer and M. Erkan Keremoglu. Cpachecker: A tool for configurable software verification. In Ganesh Gopalakrishnan and Shaz Qadeer, editors, *Computer Aided Verification*, pages 184–190, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-642-22110-1.
- [5] Dirk Beyer and Stefan Löwe. Explicit-state software model checking based on cegar and interpolation. In Vittorio Cortellessa and Dániel Varró, editors, *Fundamental Approaches to Software Engineering*, pages 146–162, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2013. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-642-37057-1.
- [6] Dirk Beyer, Alessandro Cimatti, Alberto Griggio, M Erkan Keremoglu, and Roberto Sebastiani. Software model checking via large-block encoding. In *2009 Formal Methods in Computer-Aided Design*, pages 25–32. IEEE, 2009.
- [7] Dirk Beyer, Stefan Löwe, and Philipp Wendler. Benchmarking and resource measurement for software verification. In *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems (TACAS)*, volume 10806 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 160–177. Springer, 2018. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-89963-3_10.
- [8] Dirk Beyer, Po-Chun Chien, and Nian-Ze Lee. Bridging hardware and software analysis with btor2c: A word-level-circuit-to-c translator. In *International Conference on Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems*, pages 152–172. Springer, 2023.
- [9] Armin Biere. Bounded model checking. In *Handbook of satisfiability*, pages 739–764. IOS press, 2021.
- [10] Armin Biere, Alessandro Cimatti, Edmund Clarke, and Yunshan Zhu. Symbolic model checking without bdds. In *International conference on tools and algorithms for the construction and analysis of systems*, pages 193–207. Springer, 1999.
- [11] Armin Biere, Keijo Heljanko, and Siert Wieringa. Aiger 1.9 and beyond. 2011.

- [12] Armin Biere, Norbert Froykys, and Mathias Preiner. HWMCC’25: Hardware Model Checking Competition 2025, 2025. URL <https://hwmcc.github.io/2025/>. Accessed: 2025-10-17.
- [13] Robert S Boyer and J Strother Moore. *A computational logic handbook: Formerly notes and reports in computer science and applied mathematics*. Elsevier, 2014.
- [14] Robert Brayton and Alan Mishchenko. Abc: An academic industrial-strength verification tool. In *International Conference on Computer Aided Verification*, pages 24–40. Springer, 2010.
- [15] Jerry R Burch, Edmund M Clarke, Kenneth L McMillan, David L Dill, and Lain-Jinn Hwang. Symbolic model checking: 1020 states and beyond. *Information and computation*, 98(2):142–170, 1992.
- [16] Gianpiero Cabodi, Paolo Enrico Camurati, Marco Palena, and Paolo Pasini. Hardware model checking algorithms and techniques. *Algorithms*, 17(6), 2024. ISSN 1999-4893. DOI: 10.3390/a17060253. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4893/17/6/253>.
- [17] Alessandro Cimatti, Alberto Griggio, Bastiaan Joost Schaafsma, and Roberto Sebastiani. The mathsat5 smt solver. In *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems (TACAS)*, volume 7795 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 93–107. Springer, 2013. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-36742-7_7.
- [18] Edmund M Clarke. Model checking. In *International conference on foundations of software technology and theoretical computer science*, pages 54–56. Springer, 1997.
- [19] Edmund M. Clarke, William Klieber, Miloš Nováček, and Paolo Zuliani. *Model Checking and the State Explosion Problem*, pages 1–30. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2012. ISBN 978-3-642-35746-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-35746-6_1. URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-35746-6_1.
- [20] E. Allen Emerson. *The Beginning of Model Checking: A Personal Perspective*, pages 27–45. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. ISBN 978-3-540-69850-0. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-69850-0_2. URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69850-0_2.
- [21] Mikhail R. Gadelha, Felipe R. Monteiro, Jeremy Morse, Lucas C. Cordeiro, Bernd Fischer, and Denis A. Nicole. ESBMC 5.0: an industrial-strength C model checker. In *Proceedings of the 33rd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Automated Software Engineering, ASE ’18*, page 888–891, New York, NY, USA, 2018. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450359375. DOI: 10.1145/3238147.3240481. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3238147.3240481>.
- [22] Aman Goel and Karem Sakallah. AVR: Abstractly verifying reachability. In Armin Biere and David Parker, editors, *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems*, pages 413–422, Cham, 2020. Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-030-45190-5.
- [23] John Harrison. Theorem proving for verification (invited tutorial). In *International Conference on Computer Aided Verification*, pages 11–18. Springer, 2008.
- [24] Andreas Kuehlmann and Florian Krohm. Equivalence checking using cuts and heaps. In *Proceedings of the 34th annual Design Automation Conference*, pages 263–268, 1997.

- [25] Azad M Madni and Michael Sievers. Model-based systems engineering: Motivation, current status, and research opportunities. *Systems Engineering*, 21(3):172–190, 2018.
- [26] Kenneth L McMillan. Interpolation and sat-based model checking. In *International Conference on Computer Aided Verification*, pages 1–13. Springer, 2003.
- [27] Rajdeep Mukherjee, Daniel Kroening, and Tom Melham. Hardware verification using software analyzers. In *2015 IEEE Computer Society Annual Symposium on VLSI*, pages 7–12, 2015. DOI: 10.1109/ISVLSI.2015.107.
- [28] Rajdeep Mukherjee, Michael Tautschnig, and Daniel Kroening. v2c—a verilog to c translator. In *International Conference on Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems*, pages 580–586. Springer, 2016.
- [29] Aina Niemetz, Mathias Preiner, Clifford Wolf, and Armin Biere. Btor2 , btormc and boolector 3.0. In Hana Chockler and Georg Weissenbacher, editors, *Computer Aided Verification*, pages 587–595, Cham, 2018. Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-319-96145-3.
- [30] Terence Parr, Peter Wells, Ric Klaren, Loring Craymer, Jim Coker, Scott Stanchfield, John Mitchell, and Chapman Flack. What’s antlr, 2004.
- [31] Jendrik Seipp and Malte Helmert. Counterexample-guided cartesian abstraction refinement. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Automated Planning and Scheduling*, volume 23, pages 347–351, 2013.
- [32] Mary Sheeran, Satnam Singh, and Gunnar Stålmarmark. Checking safety properties using induction and a sat-solver. In *International conference on formal methods in computer-aided design*, pages 127–144. Springer, 2000.
- [33] Tamás Tóth, Ákos Hajdu, András Vörös, Zoltán Micskei, and István Majzik. Theta: a framework for abstraction refinement-based model checking. In Daryl Stewart and Georg Weissenbacher, editors, *Proceedings of the 17th Conference on Formal Methods in Computer-Aided Design*, pages 176–179, 2017. ISBN 978-0-9835678-7-5. DOI: 10.23919/FMCAD.2017.8102257.
- [34] Clifford Wolf, Johann Glaser, and Johannes Kepler. Yosys—a free verilog synthesis suite. In *Proceedings of the 21st Austrian Workshop on Microelectronics (Austrochip)*, volume 97, 2013.

6.2 Declaration on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence

I have not used any generative AI tools.

I have used generative AI tools. I have verified the content generated by AI, ensured the accuracy of the outputs, and properly indicated each instance of use in the table below.

Usage type	Name of Generative AI Tool(s)	Affected Sections (chapter, page number, reference)	Estimate Proportion of Use (per usage type)
Literature Review	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Program Code Generation	Gemini 3 Pro	Ch. 4 Figures	3%
Brief Summary of the Prompt	Generating and refining Python plotting scripts (matplotlib, seaborn). For example: "I need to visualize the correlations between my performance metrics (CPU Time, Memory) and complexity metrics (Variable Count, Atomic Stmts, Iterations). Please write Python code using Seaborn to make a heatmap.." If we take into account all of the program code used in this thesis (including the BTOR2CFA transformation) that is about 3% of generated code.		
Generating New Ideas or Solution Proposals	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Creating an Outline (text structure, bullet points)	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Creating Text Blocks	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Generating Images for Illustrative Purposes	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Data Visualization, Generating Charts Based on Data Points	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Preparing a Presentation	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Other (please specify)	-	-	-
Brief Summary of the Prompt			
Aggregated Percentage Value (for the core part of the task):			3%
Brief Textual Justification of the Aggregated Value:			
<p>The content generated by generative AI had a minor impact on the substantive part of the thesis tasks; it was used primarily as an editor and for generating Python visualization scripts. The core implementation of the BTOR2CFA tool, the experimental setup, the selection of benchmarks, the raw data collection, and the interpretation of results were performed entirely by me. The AI assisted in writing the code to plot the visual data, but the scientific findings and analysis remain the result of my work.</p> <p>Based on the above, the estimated total proportion of content generated by generative AI in relation to the substantive part of the task is 3%.</p>			